

A GUIDE FOR NEW DATA STEWARDS

Data Infrastructure at Large-Scale Research Facilities

Whilst each large-scale research facility will have its own unique data infrastructure, there are by necessity many commonalities between them.

This guide offers insight into the types of systems to expect and how data typically flows through an institution. It serves as an introduction to data infrastructure for data stewards, and other data professionals, who are new in their role and into the area of data management.

KEYWORDS: data, infrastructure, facility, institute, research, experiment, matter, data stewards, onboarding

DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

This guide focuses on data infrastructure within large facilities. For further information and instruction on other aspects of data stewardship, please see the [Self-Directed Onboarding Guide for Research Field Matter Data Stewards and Data Managers](#).

OVERVIEW

Whilst each large-scale research facility will have its own unique data infrastructure, there are by necessity many commonalities between them. This guide offers insight into the types of systems to expect and how data typically flows through an institution.

As a data steward, your role is to support the scientists using your facility to produce high quality data that follows FAIR principles. To do this, you will need to understand the specific infrastructure that you are working within.

The aim of this guide is to help you to know which questions to ask and which systems to look for. It is written from the perspective of a Photon and Neutron (PaN) facility, but the key infrastructure is consistent across the majority of large-scale facilities. It cannot specify the exact programs or databases you will encounter, but it can help you understand what to look for.

To apply this guide effectively to your situation, focus on understanding the *function* of each system, and establish how that function is being performed or handled in your facility.

Effective data management requires the use of Persistent Identifiers, or PIDs, for anything that needs to be tracked throughout and beyond the experiment. This guide will highlight their use in some areas, but is not an exhaustive treatment of how PIDs are implemented across systems.

Please note that *data* here incorporates all digital information handled by a facility, so includes both *experimental data* and all *metadata*.

Further reading

- This guide approximately follows the data lifecycle of facilities as published in PaNdata: B. Matthews, G. Kourousias, E. Yang, and T. Griffin, ‘Model of the data continuum in Photon and Neutron Facilities’, Sep. 2012, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.3897190](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3897190).
- This is used in N. Soler et al., ‘Final recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management’, Jul. 2022, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.6821676](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6821676). This paper is a good resource for data stewards and recommended as a guide to data management best practice.
- The use and requirements of the systems within a facility is governed by the Data Policy for that facility. Further information on data policies can be found in Ö. Özkan et al, ‘Self-Directed Onboarding Guide for Research Field Matter Data Stewards and Data Managers’, Jul 2025, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.16420570](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16420570). It is important to find and familiarise yourself with the data policy for your institute.

DATA IN A WORKFLOW

Experiment proposal and setup

Typically, the data lifecycle begins at the digital user office via a **user portal**. This addresses, among other things, the proposal submission, the peer review process of the proposals, and the scheduling of experiments. Proposals necessarily include which experimental station (e.g. which beamline) is requested and which experimental techniques will be employed, both of which determine the data types that will be created.

For successful proposals, additional information may be needed to prepare for the experiment. This includes experimental setup requirements, information about the samples being tested or measured, and declarations for any hazardous materials. Where an experiment requires changing conditions, the experimental plan for, e.g., temperature or pressure changes, or the introduction of different gases, will also need to be submitted by the user. Any additional personnel will also need to be declared, so that access can be correctly granted. Most of this information will also be stored in the **user portal**.

Some facilities will have additional **experiment preparation systems**, such as a dedicated sample database or an experimental plan submission platform. This is an opportunity for users to provide information such as existing PIDs for their samples, or for the user or facility to mint such PIDs as appropriate. Such elements are crucial in order to ultimately produce FAIR data.

In order to control access to an experiment (and its data) some form of **identity management** is required. This may be achieved through the **user portal** or **metadata catalogue** (see below), or it may involve a dedicated system. Access may only be possible on-site through the facility’s network, but in most cases there will be a remote login service, most likely combined with the digital security of the facility.

A typical setup will delegate the authorisation - what data an individual can access - to the user portal or metadata catalogue, whilst the authentication - the security of the system - will be handled by the facility identity management system. Identification of an individual, such as when a log entry is made, can come from either side of this setup, but this should be consistent within the facility.

During the experiment

Once the experimental time comes around, there will be a procedure for experiment initiation. Whilst this is not directly part of the data infrastructure, it will set up, for example, the short-term storage disc space and access to the data and instrument controls.

During the experiment itself, the data acquisition finally occurs. This entails recording the output from the detectors and sensors, alongside any additional metadata such as timings and environmental factors. The experiment control systems may handle the various data sources automatically. Formats and data sizes will vary between instruments and measurement techniques.

In many cases, some data processing is applied as data is acquired, such as normalisation or noise reduction. The processed datasets are usually fed back into the process and are included in the data acquisition datasets.

In parallel there should also be an electronic lab notebook (ELN), somewhere for the experimenters to make notes and observations which preserves the order and time-stamps every entry. The ELN may be integrated to allow the control systems to automatically input messages or limited data, as required. Some ELNs allow photos or graphics to be included, some can handle Python scripts to produce graphs or other analysis, whilst some are intended only as a simple, chronological record and do not accept more complex input.

Whilst data acquisition takes place locally at the experiment, the data is quickly saved to a more suitable storage space, the short-term storage. This may take place almost instantly as readings are taken, or at latest it will happen when the experiment is marked as finished and the local spaces are closed or removed (through a procedure that mirrors experiment initiation). If a specific file format is required, conversion to this format may take place at this stage.

Further reading

- DAPHNE4NFDI has developed recommended requirements for ELNs in PaN facilities: P. Jordt et al., ‘Specifications for Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) in the Photon and Neutron Community’, *Synchrotron Radiation News*, vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 3–8, Nov. 2024, doi: [10.1080/08940886.2024.2432265](https://doi.org/10.1080/08940886.2024.2432265).
 - A supplementary paper provides additional discussion: Jordt, P., *Supplementary Information for Publication: Specifications for Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) in the Photon and Neutron Community*, Jan. 2025, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.13891465](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13891465).
- With the wide variety of data formats available, choosing to convert all data to a single format is a sensible option. Selecting a suitable format is crucial. DAPHNE4NFDI has produced some metadata recommendations to help guide this process: W. Lohstroh et al., ‘DAPHNE4NFDI - Draft recommendations on metadata capture and specifications’, Jun. 2024, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.12169109](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12169109).

Data access after the experiment

The short-term storage that now holds the data is usually accessible remotely, and is where experimenters will access and analyse their data immediately after conclusion of the experiment. This storage contains all the data and metadata acquired, including processed data where applicable, and will often include the ELN exported to a static format (such as PDF). (If the ELN is not exported it will likely be stored in a separate database, which should be identified and incorporated into the facility data management.) ‘Short-term’ usually refers to a pre-agreed number of months after the end of the experiment, during which the data will remain instantly available. If longer access is required this would be requested of the facility by the experiment personnel, and would follow the data policy of the facility. The short-term storage infrastructure may include analysis tools and software, the results of which are added to the total data.

Finally, the data is sent to the long-term archive. This can be done at any time, and in many cases data will be copied to the archive simultaneously with being saved to the short-term storage. Alternatively there could be a manual procedure to initiate the transfer. Additionally the data could be copied across automatically when the short-term storage is closed down. Whichever timing and method is preferred, there must be checks to ensure data is archived and is not accidentally lost, particularly any processed or analysed datasets that are added throughout the workflow.

The final transfer between short-term storage and the long-term archive is usually the latest point at which PIDs can be routinely minted. Throughout the workflow, it is possible to include PID creation as required - for example, for samples, instruments, proposals, or datasets - and pre-existing PIDs should be used whenever they are available. It is important to integrate PID minting early in the data lifecycle where appropriate, to ensure consistent tracking and reliable data linkage throughout the infrastructure.

Various PID systems exist, with common options including Handle, DOI (Digital Object Identifier) and IGSN (for samples) via providers like DataCite, and facility-specific solutions linked to institutional repositories or catalogues. Identifying where and how PIDs are generated in your workflow - and whether they are manually triggered or automatically minted - is key to ensuring persistent, citable, and FAIR data assets.

The long-term archive is typically not instantly accessible. Data will be stored in a more robust physical form, such as on tape, and must be reloaded onto a short-term system to be used. Requests to access archived data may take several hours, or even days, to be fulfilled. Once accessible again (usually once more in the short-term storage system), data will be available for only an agreed limited time. The long-term archive can be used to store data (including metadata and ELN records) indefinitely, so long as it is properly managed and storage media is replaced as needed (e.g. transferring data to new tapes approximately every 5 years). In Germany, good scientific practice as laid out by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) is to keep data for a minimum of 10 years. Many institutes will keep data beyond the 10-year mark, and maybe significantly longer for published data; conditions for longer storage will be laid out in the data policy for the institute.

The final piece of the puzzle is the metadata catalogue. This is a database that has a record of all the data in the long-term archive. It doesn't store the *experimental data*, rather it contains all the *metadata* required to search for and identify the data. So anyone looking for data from a particular type of experiment or using a particular material (or any other parameters) would search in the metadata catalogue. This would then provide a list of which datasets are relevant to the search, which can then be requested from the long-term archive.

Data is usually initially under an embargo period, during which the facility cannot make it public. This allows researchers time to use and publish their findings before sharing the data. The default embargo period is often 3-5 years for research data, whilst industry data would be under an indefinite embargo and should never become public unless the industry user chooses to make it public. Embargo periods can usually be shortened upon request; increasing the embargo period for research data usually requires extenuating circumstances since making the data public is part of the facility-use agreement. Once again, the data policy of the institute would lay out the terms of the embargo period.

As such, the metadata catalogue will usually operate some form of access control and identity management. This allows researchers to use the metadata catalogue to find and request their own data before the embargo period expires. (All data not under embargo is publicly available and can be requested by anyone.) As a result, in some facilities the authorisation throughout the experiment may be controlled through the architecture of the metadata catalogue by initialising a catalogue record for the experiment at the beginning of the process.

SUMMARY OF SYSTEMS

- **User portal, typically including:**
 - Proposal system, to apply for experimental time at the facility
 - Record of users, linked to their proposals and experiments
- **Experiment preparation systems**
 - Any method of recording user-supplied data that is relevant to the experiment
 - Could include equipment setup, sample information, hazardous materials declarations, temperature or pressure requirements, etc
 - Additionally, safety requirements or training will be recorded
 - May be contained within the **user portal**
- **Identity management**
 - Used to control access and authorisation to instruments and data
 - May be distributed across multiple systems
 - May include a single sign-on (SSO) service
- **Experiment initiation**
 - *Not strictly part of the data infrastructure, but integrates with it*
 - *Used to trigger creation of, e.g., experimental workspace and storage structure*
- **Data acquisition**
 - Any system recording the data from the sensors and detectors during the experiment
 - Any system recording associated metadata during the experiment
- **Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN)**
 - Records notes and observations from experimenters
 - May also include automated messages from the experiment systems
- **Short-term storage**
 - Instant access storage for experimental data and metadata
 - Typically data is sent here directly from acquisition; data may be converted to a different format before being sent
 - This storage is usually available for a pre-agreed period after the end of the experiment

- **Long-term archive**

- Archived data is not instant-access as it is stored in an inaccessible form, e.g. on tape
- Data is only available upon request, as it must first be uploaded back to the short-term storage system to be accessible
- Data is typically kept for 10+ years; some data may be kept indefinitely

- **Metadata catalogue**

- Record of the data in the archive
- Includes enough metadata to identify the datasets, and for datasets to appear in relevant searches
- Used to find and request data from the long-term archive
- Access control required for data under an embargo period

DISCOVERING THE INFRASTRUCTURE AT YOUR FACILITY

It is very important, as a data professional, to become acquainted with the data infrastructure at your facility. Below are some tips on what to look for and what to ask to get a complete picture.

- **Terminology will vary.** The terms used in this guide are not universal. The descriptions should allow you to understand what core function each system performs, and to identify the equivalent functions and the systems performing them in your facility.
- **If something is missing** ask how the function is handled at your facility. Some functions may be unnecessary, others may be combined into a single system.
- **Identify how data flows** through your facility.
 - What data is brought in from outside, where does it come from, how is it incorporated into the facility's systems?
 - What is needed and what is produced in terms of data at each stage of the process?
 - Where does data go? Where is it stored, and how is it accessed?
- **You don't need to know the detail of every system.** Some systems will be managed by different departments and be part of other infrastructures. Knowing that they exist and who to go to when you need information about them will often be sufficient.
- **You don't know what you don't know!** You can only ask about things that you are aware of. This guide is intended to help you find out what exists and what it does in terms of data infrastructure. This will allow you, in the future, to have the awareness to ask the right questions.